

Computer Aided Diagnosis and Machine Learning in Breast Cancer Detection

An overview of how machine learning and computer aided diagnosis systems can improve the early detection of breast cancer.

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to provide an overview of how artificial intelligence can help in diagnosing breast cancer. We introduce the different stages in which computer aided diagnostic systems work and how machine learning can help in diagnosing pathological patterns.

According to the American Cancer Society, breast cancer is the most common cancer in women in the United States, except for skin cancer. It is about 1 in 3 of each new female diagnosed cancer each year, and they estimated that around 43,250 women die in 2022 from breast cancer alone.[1]

The average risk of developing breast cancer is about 13%, which means that round 1 in 8 women will develop breast cancer in their lifetime.[1]

Early detection and diagnosis of breast cancer is crucial for effective treatment and improved patient outcomes. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the use of machine learning and computer assisted diagnosis systems for breast cancer detection. These systems can improve the accuracy and efficiency of breast cancer diagnosis and can be useful in resource-limited settings.

Overall, the use of machine learning and computer-assisted diagnosis can significantly improve breast cancer detection and diagnosis and represents a promising direction for future research and development in the field.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 How Mammography works

Mammography is a widely used imaging modality for the early detection of breast cancer. It involves the use of low-energy X-rays to produce detailed images of the breast tissue. During a mammogram, the breast is compressed between two plates to spread the breast tissue out and make it easier to examine. This compression is necessary to produce high-quality images and to reduce the amount of radiation exposure.

After the mammogram is completed, a radiologist will interpret the images to look for any signs of breast cancer. This process can be subjective and is prone to error, leading to missed diagnoses and false positives. Data science techniques, such as machine learning and CAD, are being developed to improve the accuracy

and efficiency of mammography breast cancer detection. CAD Software has been developed and has been in clinical use since 1998 [2] and it has been disseminated into practice.

1.2 Computer Aided Diagnosis

Computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) is a technology that uses computer algorithms to analyze medical images and provide a recommendation for further evaluation or treatment. In the context of mammography breast cancer detection, CAD systems are used to analyze mammogram images and flag any abnormalities that may be indicative of breast cancer. It is a promising way to improve the predictive capabilities of histopathologists by providing a reliable second opinion and showing areas on the breasts which should be given special attention.

In research to diagnose breast cancer there exist different techniques for screening anomalies. [3] Mainly Mammograms and computerized tomography using x-rays of certain wavelengths, magnetic resonance imaging, ultrasound using soundwaves etc.

CAD systems for mammography are typically trained on data sets of labeled mammograms, with the labels indicating the presence or absence of breast cancer. The CAD system uses these labeled images to learn how to identify patterns and features indicative of breast cancer. These systems can be used to help radiologists interpret mammograms and can reduce the rate of missed diagnoses.

2. Machine Learning in CAD Systems.

There are 4 essential parts to CAD Systems, excluding Image Acquisition for breast cancer detection [4]

2.1 Pre-Processing

This phase converts the data into a structure in which the images are made so that they can be better analyzed further. Corrections to the image are common to reduce the variation between the images. As an example, in the RSNA Screening Mammography Breast Cancer Detection Dataset from a Kaggle challenge of the Radiological Society of North America [5] for some of the machines the background values are switched.

[6]

2.2 Segmentation

The process of segmentation divides an image into distinct, non-overlapping regions. This is done to separate the objects of interest from the background, using techniques such as clustering, edge detection, thresholding, and region growing. The specific technique used for segmentation depends on the features that need to be extracted. [7]

There are several segmentation methods in the literature that have been utilized for diagnosing breast cancer using histopathological images. Some commonly employed segmentation techniques include thresholding [8], clustering [9], active contour model [10], level set, watershed algorithm [[11], and neural networks. [6] [4]

2.3 Feature Extraction

Feature extraction involves identifying distinctive, invariant features in the input. [12] After segmenting the image, features can be extracted at the tissue or cellular level. Commonly used features include intensity, fractal, textural, and morphological features. To extract features at the cellular level, the locations of cells must be identified in advance. At the tissue level, fractal, topological, and textural features can be extracted to measure changes.

Some of the most common types of features used are textural, graph-based, intensity, morphological, and network-based features. [4]

Textural features are important for identifying regions of interest (ROI) in images. These features can be calculated using the grayscale values of the entire image or just the ROI. Textural features, such as contrast, dissimilarity, autocorrelation, energy, and difference variance, can be used to differentiate between grades of cancer, as cancerous tissue often has an increased number of nuclei. Textural features can be extracted using techniques such as the Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM), Haralick, Gabor filter, Local Binary Pattern (LBP), Parameter-Free Threshold Adjacency Statistics (PFTAS), Grey level, Local Phase Quantization (LPQ), and Short Run Emphasis (SRE) [13] [14] [4] [15]. These techniques can be applied to histopathological images to classify benign and malignant breast cancer images and to distinguish between high and low grades of malignancy.

2.4 Classification

Classification is the process of categorizing new instances based on a training dataset. It is used to diagnose abnormalities in images by categorizing tissues into distinct categories of breast cancer or grades. Tissues or cells in an image are classified into one of several classes, such as benign, malignant, or cancerous with different grading. Techniques for classification include K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), fuzzy systems, neural networks, and logistic regression.[4] These can be applied to histopathological images to classify them as benign or malignant.

3 Improvements through Machine Learning

In the last years, improvements to machine learning techniques have significantly improved the predictive power and accuracy of CAD systems.

In 2007 the conclusion of a paper on the Influence of Computer-Aided Detection on Performance of Screening Mammography has concluded that “The use of computer-aided detection is associated with reduced accuracy of interpretation of screening mammograms. The increased rate of biopsy with the use of computer-aided detection is not clearly associated with improved detection of invasive breast cancer.” [[2]

In comparison a study published 2018 which aggregated the results of studies on using CAD for detection of breast cancer [16] found that “All but two studies from the Single Reading (SR) vs. SR + CAD group showed an increased sensitivity and/or cancer detection rate (CDR) when adding CAD. The Double Reading (DR) vs. SR + CAD group showed no significant differences in sensitivity and CDR. Adding CAD to SR increased the Diagnostic Accuracy and Recall Rates (RR) and decreased the specificity in all but one study. For the DR vs. SR + CAD group only one study reported a significant difference in RR.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the use of machine learning and computer assisted diagnosis has the potential to significantly improve the accuracy and efficiency of breast cancer detection and diagnosis. These approaches have shown promising results in numerous studies and can significantly impact patient outcomes by enabling early detection and treatment of breast cancer. However, more research is needed to optimize these approaches in clinical practice and to address any potential challenges and limitations. Overall, the use of machine learning and computer assisted diagnosis for breast cancer detection represents a promising direction for future research and development in the field and has the potential to impact the care and treatment of patients with breast cancer.

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